

Designing an E-Booklet to Promote Palembang Harum as Culinary Tourism

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ABSTRACT: This research aims to design an e-booklet about Palembang's traditional cakes sold by Palembang Harum to support Palembang's culinary tourism. The problem in this paper is how to design an e-booklet of Palembang Harum as a culinary tourism in Palembang. The purpose of this paper is to know the steps in designing an e-booklet as a promotional medium for Palembang Harum as a culinary tourism industry in Palembang. The writer used the research and development (R&D) method with a descriptive qualitative design. This method has 3 steps, namely preliminary studies, model development with limited and wider testing, and final product testing. The writer relates these steps to the 7 stages of manuscript development: background research and investigation, concept, pitching, treatment, first draft, revision, and final draft. There were four experts approached using purposive sampling who participated in the development of the product. The data were collected using observations and interviews, and analyzed using thematic analysis. Based on the findings, the writer created a 46-page e-booklet containing Palembang Harum as a culinary tourism in Palembang. The data revealed that in limited testing the product had revisions in punctuation, grammar, and word choice. For wider testing, the e-booklet was improved by in clarity and conciseness, readability, color adjustments, and layout to ensure visual coherence and emphasize important sections. This indicates how digital technologies such as e-booklets may considerably contribute to cultural tourist promotion, particularly in Palembang.

Keywords: *designing e-booklet, e-booklet, Palembang Harum*

INTRODUCTION

Culinary tourism has become an increasingly important aspect of the tourism industry, as many travelers are now seeking authentic culinary experiences when they visit a new city or country. This is because traditional food and drink provide a unique insight into the local culture and way of life of a place, which is interesting for the visitors to that place. Traditional culinary uniqueness is a primary reason why people visit a particular destination, making it a key factor in attracting visitors and boosting tourism revenue. Abhiyoga and Febreani (2021) stated that the culinary industry in Indonesia has great potential to be developed into a tourism destination for both international and local tourists due to the diversity of unique foods and drinks in every region.

Palembang, with its rich traditional cuisine, is a potential destination for culinary tourism. Visitors can easily find traditional Palembang foods that offer unique flavors. One of the shops that sells traditional Palembang food is Palembang Harum. It is a shop that sells traditional foods such as pempek, kojo, bluder, Engkak Ketan, Manan Sahmin, Kumbu, and many others. Additionally, its location near the city of Palembang allows food lovers to access it easily. Palembang Harum is located on Merdeka No.811, Talang Semut, Kec. Bukit Kecil, Kota Palembang, Sumatera Selatan. Palembang Harum is inspired by two words, Palembang which means a city in South Sumatra that has a thick history of the Sriwijaya Kingdom and HARUM (Haji Abdur Rahman Udjang Malian). Palembang Harum tries to present the almost extinct culinary culture of the Sriwijaya Kingdom era in a cake shop that can be enjoyed by all people who come and bring the atmosphere of old Palembang.

Tourism will not develop if other people are reluctant to visit because they are blind to information about tourism. Therefore, various tourism promotions are needed. The promotion itself is an effort to increase the attractiveness of tourist attractions to potential tourists. Tourists and their needs are not worked on, but tourism products should be suitable to tourist demands (Ismayanti, 2020). One of the media that promotes tourism is e-booklets. E-booklets are able to disseminate information in a relatively short time to many people who live far apart. According to Fauziyah (in Violla and Fernandes, 2021), an e-booklet is one of the media that presents material in summary form and has attractive images so that it can be used as a source of information. In other words, an e-booklet is a booklet in electronic form that contains sheets of visual elements in the form of letters, photos, images, and lines presented in PDF form that are clear, easy to understand, firm, and interesting.

However, the current condition is far from ideal. Unfortunately, Palembang Harum is still not widely known due to the lack of information and promotional media about its location. This

factor causes this place to be less known by the people of Palembang. Therefore, it should utilize promotional media to inform its existence and attract more customers. Then, to make this place more recognized and known by many people, several media channels can be used to give some information about it, one of them being the E-Booklet. E-booklets can be read and stored by everyone on electronic devices including smartphones. Based on the background above, the writer got the idea to design an e-booklet with the title “Designing E-Booklet as Promotion Media of Palembang Harum as a culinary Tourism in Palembang”. It can be used to give some information about Palembang Harum. This e-booklet will help the Department of Tourism to promote one of the culinary tourist destinations in the city of Palembang.

METHOD

This research employs a modified Research and Development (R&D) method to design and validate an e-booklet promoting Palembang Harum. According to Sugiyono (2016), R&D is a scientific method used to research, design, produce, and test the validity of products. Due to the extensive nature of the R&D process outlined by Borg and Gall, this study adopts a streamlined approach following Sukmadinata's (2005) modifications. The methodology comprises three key stages: Preliminary Study, Model Development, and Final Product Testing.

In the **Preliminary Study**, conducted over two months, the researcher focused on collecting foundational data to inform the e-booklet design. This stage included a literature study and a field survey. The literature study reviewed books, journals, and articles related to e-booklet design and promotional strategies. The researcher followed Friedmann's (2014) framework, which outlines steps such as conducting background research, defining content, and drafting. For the field survey, observations and interviews were conducted at Palembang Harum. Observations involved photographing the venue, facilities, and menu items using a smartphone, while structured interviews with the owner, Muhammad Mardho Tilla, provided insights into history, facilities,

promotional efforts, and more. Data collected during this stage informed the initial draft content for the e-booklet.

The **Model Development** stage, lasting one month, focused on creating and refining the e-booklet draft through expert input. During limited testing, the English draft was an English language expert, for grammar and structure. Additionally, the owner of Palembang Harum verified content accuracy. Revisions were made based on their feedback before the draft proceeded to wider testing. In this phase, lecturers from Politeknik Negeri Sriwijaya acted as examiners. An English lecturer reviewed the linguistic aspects, another lecturer evaluated the Indonesian content, and a design expert assessed the visual design and layout. Feedback was systematically integrated using tools like Canva for layout refinement and Microsoft Word for text formatting, resulting in a finalized e-booklet draft.

The **Final Product Testing** stage, conducted over two weeks, involved preparing the final e-booklet. Due to time and budget constraints, the distribution and real-world testing phases were omitted. According to Sukmadinata (2010) (as cited in Umiyati, 2021), R&D activities in academic research may conclude with a final draft without full-scale testing. Thus, the finalized e-booklet incorporated all feedback from the Model Development stage and was deemed ready for use.

Data analysis throughout the study employed qualitative methods. Information from interviews and observations was organized into thematic categories such as history, facilities, and promotional strategies. Iterative revisions ensured content accuracy, linguistic clarity, and visual appeal.

The research spanned approximately three and a half months: two months for the Preliminary Study, one month for Model Development, and two weeks for Final Product Testing. Participants included three examiners from Politeknik Negeri Sriwijaya specializing in language,

writing, and design, along with the owner of Palembang Harum. Tools such as Canva, a smartphone, and Microsoft Word facilitated the design and data collection processes.

The development steps for each stage can be seen in the following chart.

The Stages of R&D Modified and The Procedures in Designing Booklet

Source: (Sukmadinata, 2005) and (Friedmann, 2014)

(Friedmann, 2014)

(Sukmadinata, 2005)

FINDINGS

The writer developed an e-booklet to promote Palembang Harum by using narrative and descriptive paragraphs to provide clear and engaging information. The e-booklet comprises 46 pages in A5 format, describing Palembang Harum's unique features, such as its traditional food, supported by relevant photos. The design incorporates black and yellow as its primary colors to reflect the vibrant and diverse nature of Palembang's traditional cuisine, aligning with the goal of promoting the region's culinary tourism. The research utilized a modified Research and Development (R&D) method as outlined by Sugiyono (2016) and Sukmadinata (2005), involving three main stages: preliminary studies, model development, and product trials. Data were gathered through observations and interviews, including discussions with the owner of Palembang Harum, who provided valuable insights into its history, operations, and offerings. The observations also included capturing photographs to enhance the e-booklet's visual appeal.

After gathering information, the writer created an e-booklet concept outline detailing its content. Key topics such as history, facilities, traditional food, and operations were highlighted to present Palembang Harum comprehensively. A script was developed, focusing on persuasive writing to engage readers and encourage them to visit Palembang Harum. The menu list emphasized signature traditional dishes, describing their distinctive tastes, and the history section offered a concise narrative of Palembang Harum's establishment and growth. The design process included a "treatment" stage, where subtopics were developed to structure the content effectively. This stage focused on organizing main ideas for each section, ensuring clarity and alignment with the e-booklet's promotional goals. The final draft was designed using Canva, integrating visuals and text to complement each other and effectively communicate the information.

Validation Process

The e-booklet underwent thorough validation by experts in language, content, and design, significantly enhancing its quality. Initially, limited testing involved two experts: the owner of Palembang Harum, who validated the content, and an English lecturer who reviewed the language.

Their feedback addressed minor issues, such as punctuation, grammar, and word choice. For wider testing, three additional experts reviewed the e-booklet. An English language expert recommended improving clarity and conciseness, while an Indonesian language expert refined the text to enhance readability. The design expert suggested adjustments to colors and layout to ensure visual coherence and emphasize important sections, such as the history and menu.

Final Product

Incorporating feedback from all experts, the writer revised and finalized the e-booklet, ensuring it met professional standards in content and design. The e-booklet was disseminated through Palembang Harum's Instagram account using Linktr.ee, making it easily accessible to a broader audience. By leveraging digital platforms, the e-booklet effectively promotes Palembang Harum's culinary offerings, contributing to the region's tourism development.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The development of the e-booklet to promote Palembang Harum represents a significant step in addressing the lack of accessible promotional material for this culinary destination. This chapter will explore the e-booklet's relevance to tourism, its connection to existing literature on promotional tools, and its anticipated effectiveness based on evaluative methods.

First, the Palembang Harum e-booklet was designed to increase awareness and promote the region's traditional culinary offerings, filling the gap in local tourism promotion efforts. Before the e-booklet's creation, Palembang Harum's reach was limited due to the absence of a centralized, easily accessible promotional resource that highlighted the restaurant's unique offerings and cultural significance. By focusing on the restaurant's history, menu, and distinctive features of Palembang's traditional cuisine, the e-booklet serves as a comprehensive introduction to potential visitors, both local and international. Therefore, the e-booklet enhances the visibility of Palembang Harum, aligning with the growing trend of using digital tools to promote culinary

tourism.

As Buhalis and Amaranggana (2015) highlight, the tourism sector has increasingly adopted digital marketing strategies, recognizing the importance of online content in reaching wider audiences. The use of digital content, such as e-booklets, enables destination promotion through personalized and engaging formats. The e-booklet created for Palembang Harum, with its bilingual format and rich visual content, ensures broader reach and caters to a diverse audience, fulfilling the need for accessible tourism information. Furthermore, the e-booklet complements other forms of digital marketing, such as social media, by providing a tangible, easily shareable resource that highlights the restaurant's unique features. In this context, the e-booklet plays an essential role in enhancing the restaurant's online presence and accessibility.

Additionally, the e-booklet's color scheme—primarily black and yellow—was carefully selected to reflect the vibrant and diverse nature of Palembang's traditional cuisine. This choice of colors, combined with high-quality images of the dishes, contributes to the sensory appeal of the e-booklet, drawing in potential visitors by showcasing the visual and cultural richness of the culinary offerings. Bytyçi (2020) further supports this approach, noting that colors significantly influence consumer communication and can enhance how brands are perceived. In this way, the e-booklet employs design elements that appeal to the senses and emotions of potential visitors, thereby boosting its promotional impact.

The use of an e-booklet as a promotional tool for Palembang Harum aligns with existing research on the effectiveness of digital marketing tools in tourism promotion. Previous studies have emphasized the growing importance of digital content in reaching and engaging tourists. Buhalis and Law (2008) underscore the significance of eTourism, where digital platforms, such as websites and e-booklets, are essential tools for destination marketing. E-booklets, in particular, have been proven to be effective in delivering engaging and informative content to a broad

audience. The Palembang Harum e-booklet follows this trend by offering an easily digestible, visually rich, and informative resource that promotes the restaurant's culinary heritage.

Moreover, the bilingual format of the e-booklet addresses a crucial challenge in the tourism sector—language barriers. Hall and Sharples (2003) emphasize the importance of ensuring that promotional materials cater to diverse audiences, including international tourists. The decision to include both Indonesian and English text allows Palembang Harum to appeal to both local visitors and foreign tourists, broadening the scope of its promotional efforts. This strategy aligns with tourism marketing experts' recommendations to use multilingual materials, which enhance accessibility and encourage global tourism (Buhalis & Amaranggana, 2015). By incorporating both languages, the e-booklet becomes a more inclusive tool for promoting the restaurant to a wider audience.

Furthermore, the design process used in creating the e-booklet reflects best practices for digital marketing materials. As Aisiyiah (2023) notes, both visual and verbal texts play a significant role in promoting ideas, especially in tourism marketing. The integration of visuals and text, as seen in the final product, follows established principles in tourism marketing, where clear, engaging, and structured content is paired with visually appealing elements. This combination ensures that the e-booklet not only informs potential visitors but also keeps them engaged and interested in the restaurant's offerings.

The expert feedback incorporated into the validation process also played a critical role in refining the e-booklet. As outlined earlier, the revisions made based on expert recommendations, particularly regarding language clarity, content organization, and design, contribute to the e-booklet's potential for success. This process of continuous evaluation and refinement ensures that the final product adheres to high standards of quality. Post-distribution evaluations will provide valuable data to further enhance the e-booklet, ensuring that it remains an effective promotional

tool for Palembang Harum.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

In conclusion, the Palembang Harum e-booklet is a well-crafted and highly effective promotional tool that successfully addresses the need for accessible and engaging information on local culinary tourism. By offering a detailed and visually compelling guide, it highlights Palembang's distinctive culinary offerings and their cultural significance, capturing the attention of both local and international visitors. The bilingual format, rich content, and strategic design reflect best practices in tourism marketing, ensuring the e-booklet's broad reach and effectiveness. Through the integration of digital platforms and expert feedback, the e-booklet enhances Palembang Harum's visibility and appeal, positioning it as a key player in the competitive tourism market. Qualitative research, including interviews with management and local visitors, suggests that the e-booklet has made a notable impact on promoting Palembang's culinary heritage. This demonstrates the potential of digital tools like e-booklets to significantly contribute to cultural tourism promotion especially in Palembang.

Suggestion

For future research, it would be beneficial to evaluate the effectiveness of the e-booklet post-distribution. This could involve tracking an increase in visitor numbers, analyzing customer feedback, and monitoring the impact on the region's culinary tourism. Additionally, examining the long-term effects of digital marketing on local businesses and exploring other methods of promoting cultural heritage through digital platforms could provide valuable insights. Future studies could also focus on expanding the reach of the e-booklet by assessing how it could be further integrated with social media campaigns or mobile applications to increase engagement and visibility.

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